

Acute Phase Proteins and Their Role as Indicators of Health in Dairy Cow

Bharat S Siddhapara*, Virendra K Singh, Axay B Joshi and Prashant G Rathod
Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Navsari, Kamdhenu University, Gujarat, India

Introduction

Acute phase proteins are key regulators of acute phase response during infectious or inflammatory injuries. They may be of help for diagnosis and prognosis of disease. Dairy cows form the backbone of livestock industry therefore role of acute phase response and use of acute phase proteins for assuring the health and welfare of them is critical. Thus, this review is based on basics of acute phase proteins, acute phase response, role of APP in different diseases in dairy cows and future prospects of it.

Acute phase proteins (APPs) and acute phase response (APR)

Acute phase proteins (APPs) as early reactants to infectious disease are proteins that represent innate immune system's systemic response to infection or inflammation. They are useful for diagnosis, prognosis, assessment of health, assessing inflammatory activity and welfare of animals.

APR is an innate immune response comprising of inflammatory mediators that involves APPs and represents a congregation of highly coordinated physiological processes occurring soon after the onset of infection, injury, trauma, inflammatory processes.

Classification of acute phase proteins

Classification of APPs is broadly based on whether they are being upregulated or down regulated, their mode of action and site of their synthesis.

Based on upregulation and downregulation

Up regulated and down regulated APPs are referred as positive and negative APPs respectively. Positive acute phase proteins are further classified into subgroups as major, moderate and minor APPs depending on their increase. Some of the examples of positive APPs include

haptoglobin, Serum amyloid A, fibrinogen, ceruloplasmin, alpha-1 acid glycoprotein and alpha-1 antitrypsin and few examples of negative APPs are albumin, paraoxonase, lipoprotein, transferrin, transthyretin and retinol binding protein. As per their response during APR in bovine plasma Examples of major APPs that increase about 10–100 fold are Haptoglobin (Hp) and Serum amyloid-A (SAA), moderate APPs that include 2-10-folds are 1-acid glycoprotein (1-AG) and 1-proteinase inhibitor (1-PI) and minor APPs that increase about 1-5-fold increase are fibrinogen, ceruloplasmin, α 2-macroglobulin (α 2-M), complement component 3 (C₃) and bovine lipopolysaccharide binding protein (bLBP).

Based on their mode of action

Depending on their mode of action they are classified as Protease inhibitors (eg. Alpha 1 antitrypsin, Alpha 1 antichymotrypsin), Coagulation proteins (Fibrinogen, Prothrombin), complement proteins (C₂, C₃, C₄, C₅), transport proteins (Hp, Cp, Hemopexin) and other proteins such as CRP, SAA, SAP and AGP.

Based on site of synthesis

Based on their site of synthesis, APPs are classified as hepatic APPs (synthesized in liver) or extra hepatic synthesis (synthesized at sites other than liver) such as epithelial cell, endothelial cells and connective tissues.

Functions of some acute phase proteins

C- reactive protein (CRP)

They play roles in activities of monocytes and macrophages, chromatin binding, preventing tissue migration of neutrophils, cytokinin production as well as complement activation and opsonization.

Haptoglobin (Hp)

They have roles in stimulation of angiogenesis, being bacteriostatic, decrease in chemotaxis and ROS generation, chaperon activity, increased anti-inflammatory mediator and decreased LOX/COX activities.

Serum amyloid A (SAA)

They have roles to increase in intestinal mucin, modulating increase in chemotaxis, opsonizing of bacteria, binding as well as scavenging of cholesterol, inhibition effects on fever and inhibiting *in vitro* immune response.

Fibrinogen

It is involved in homeostasis, formation of fibrin as well as tissue repair, migration of inflammatory-related cells, degranulation, phagocytosis, antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity and delay of apoptosis.

Alpha 1 acid glycoprotein

They play role in binding and transport, antibacterial action, chaperon activities, reduction in chemotaxis, ROS, apoptosis and increased TNF-alpha and IL8 production.

Ceruloplasmin (Cp)

They cause decreased ROS and toxic product of iron, antioxidant action, remodeling of extracellular matrix and resolution of granulation tissue.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin (AAT)

AAT is most common serine protease inhibitor (serpin). It plays part as proteinase inhibitor in inhibition of leukocyte elastase and reaction with elastin.

Lactoferrin

It binds and transfers Fe^{3+} ions more efficiently than transferrin, represents initial defense systems mostly via mucosal tissues in mammary gland against microbes.

Albumin

It functions as an antioxidant, Immuno-modulation, role in osmotic pressure, functions of antithrombosis, stabilization of endothelial lining and roles in binding & transport.

Transferrin (Tf)

Its roles are in transporting iron for growing cells of the body. Plasma Tf acts as source of supply of iron for body tissues.

Transthyretin (TTR)

Its roles include protection against ischemic effects, maintenance of mammary, maintaining cognition and neuritogenic activities, roles in mastitis and subclinical mastitis as well as transport of Vitamin A and thyroid hormone.

Acute phase proteins as indicators of common health problems in dairy cows

Mastitis and subclinical mastitis

Milk Hp and SAA are associated with proteolysis and lower lactose content, protein and casein indicating poor milk quality (Akerstedt *et al.*, 2008). M-SAA usefulness has been apt for diagnosis of clinical and subclinical mastitis (Kovac *et al.*, 2011). Serum Hp levels have been reported to rise during mastitis (Petersen *et al.*, 2004).

Reproduction and peripartum reproductive disorders

Peripartum is most vulnerable period and metritis is common problem during it. Hp and SAA have been commonly implicated in cows to rise after parturition. Hp rise is associated with metritis (Chan *et al.*, 2010).

Abdominal and cardiac disorders

Hp and Fbg have been found to be useful in diagnosing conditions like traumatic reticuloperitonitis in dairy cows. Hp and SAA concentrations tend to rise during pericarditis. Jafarzadeh *et al.* (2004) have reported association of Fbg with conditions like TRP, reticuloperitonitis and abomasal displacement.

Hoof diseases and lameness

An association between levels of Fbg, ceruloplasmin, Hp and seromuroid in heifer during first lactation with hemorrhage of hoof and horn was found to be correlated. Tothova *et al.* (2011) reported higher levels of Hp, SAA and Fbg in hoof diseases.

Metabolic diseases

Negative energy balance and sub-acute ruminal acidosis especially during transition are associated with oxidative stress, increased lipolysis and higher NEFA levels. Rise in SAA, Hp and lipopolysaccharide-binding protein have been implicated in dairy cows during SARA (Khafipour *et al.*, 2009).

Stress

Generalized form of stress can culminate into several other disorders and predispose dairy cows to various diseases. So, an estimation of APP levels for general health and stress is important. In calves stress is known to increase APP (Conner *et al.*, 1988) for example stress like slippery floor is sufficient to cause increase in SAA (Alsemgeest *et al.*, 1995). Transport for about 4-6 hours is reported to cause stress associated increase in Hp and SAA in cattle (Lomborg *et al.*, 2008).

Conclusion

In the absence of adequate specific studies, as non-specific markers of inflammation, APPs testing is useful to assess general health and welfare, diagnosis and prognosis of disease and efficacy of therapy. It can be of help for early diagnosis, but more than one APP is required to derive conclusive finding. Routine clinical application is limited due to cost considerations and lack of sufficient reference database.

Future perspectives

There is dire need for intensive studies so as to increase specificity and sensitivity of APPs as biomarker for various disorders and diseases in cattle as well as other species. Development of APPs analytical tests that are species specific is critical. It is important to develop tests that are cheap and can be performed in field to yield rapid results.

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